

The Prognostic Values of Inflammatory Markers in Colorectal Cancer: A Prospective Study

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Abstract

Background: The Tumor-Node-Metastasis (TNM) classification system, currently the standard for identifying stages of colon cancer, is not able to adequately describe the entire prognostic variation between patients. Increasing evidence has demonstrated that the systemic inflammation is crucial in tumorigenesis and survival. The purpose of this study was to investigate the prognostic value of m-GPS and NLR as preoperative inflammatory markers for patients who underwent curative resection with colon cancer. **Methods:** A total of 210 patients with colon cancer who received curative resection treatment at single tertiary center were included in this retrospective study. The patients m-GPS and NLR values were obtained for cancer-specific survival (CSS) at five years. Survival analysis was performed using Kaplan–Meier survival curves and Cox proportional hazards methods. The main aim was to investigate the relationship of these inflammatory markers with long-term survival. Results An m-GPS of >0 was an independent predictor of CSS (HR = 3.92; 95% CI: 1.80–8.56; $p = 0.001$), while NLR did not remain significant on multivariable analysis ($p = 0.044$). Patients with m-GPS of 2 showed dramatically worse survival. Notably, the prognostic superiority of m-GPS was most evident in patients with stage II/III disease, and it may have a role as an adjunct to TNM staging for risk assessment. **Conclusions:** Our results suggest that m-GPS is a strong independent prognostic factor in CC, especially for stage II or III patients, for whom treatment can be difficult to decide. The implementation of inflammation markers, such as m-GPS, into the clinical decision-making could improve adjuvant therapy selection and the follow-up care of patients. We suggest that prospective validation studies be conducted to verify these findings.

Introduction

Globally, colorectal cancer ranks as the third most often diagnosed malignancy, impacting both men and women at considerable rates [1]. The TNM system, administered by the American Joint Committee on Cancer (AJCC), is the most universally recognized staging framework for colorectal cancer [2]. Despite the value of the TNM system, it places emphasis on the anatomical progression of cancer based upon inspection of the resection specimen and the presence

of distant metastasis on imaging [3]. There is, however, significant variation in the cancer-specific outcome between patients within each stage and patients with stage IIIA disease have a better prognosis than those with stage IIB [4]. These factors indicate that anatomical features alone are insufficient for adequate prognostication. Whilst recent advances in the field of cancer biology demonstrate the value of various histological parameters for prognostication [5], they are yet to be included in international staging systems.

More Information

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Furthermore, histological parameters suffer from significant intra-observer variability [6], are prone to sampling error, and rely on the skill of highly trained pathologists. An alternative to histopathology is the analysis of preoperative serum biochemistry or haematological parameters to assist prognostication. Both the neutrophil: lymphocyte ratio (NLR) [7] and modified Glasgow Prognostic Score (m-GPS) [8] are independent predictors of outcomes in patients with colon cancer. Such scoring systems suggest that patients with colon cancers eliciting an inflammatory response are likely to have a worse outcome and that the addition of these parameters to the TNM system may help to better identify high-risk patients. This study leverages a retrospectively collected database of colon cancer patients from a single institution to assess the prognostic significance of preoperative inflammatory markers, specifically NLR and m-GPS. We present compelling evidence that m-GPS is an independent predictor of CSS.

Methods

This study followed the STROBE (Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology) guidelines for cohort research, utilizing a retrospective design based on prospectively gathered data. The aim was to investigate if preoperative indicators of systemic inflammation act as dependable prognostic predictors in individuals receiving therapy for colon cancer.

Study Design and Setting

This is a retrospective study of patients undergoing potentially curative resection for colon cancer at Wexham Park Hospital, Slough, UK between 2009 and 2010 using data from a prospectively collected dataset. Patients were all received standard oncological and surgical treatment in a single tertiary center. Data were collected including preoperative examination, procedures and postoperative observation, as well as survival results during the 5-year period of follow-up.

Study Population

This is a retrospective study based on data extracted from a prospectively maintained dataset of patient undergoing resection with curative intention for colon cancer at Wexham Park Hospital, Slough, UK between 2009 and 2010. Patients all received standard oncologic and surgical care at a single tertiary center. Data on preoperative assessment, interventions and postoperative monitoring as well as survival in the 5-year follow-up period were recorded.

Data Collection and Variables

Clinicopathological and laboratory data were obtained from computerized medical records and a preoperative maintained prospectively kept surgical database. The stage of tumors was determined after preoperative imaging and confirmed according to the TNM staging system in the American Joint Committee on Cancer 7th Edition (AJCC). Histological characteristics of post-

resection specimens were used to determine its histopathology. Two main outcomes, cancer-specific survival (CSS), and overall survival (OS) were evaluated in the study. This study focused on two major systemic inflammation markers: modified Glasgow Prognostic Score (m-GPS) and Neutrophil-to-Lymphocyte Ratio (NLR). The m-GPS was derived from the preoperative measurements of blood, with patients being given two points if both albumin (≤ 35 g/L) and C-reactive protein (≥ 10 mg/L) were elevated, one point if only one of these markers deviated from normality, or no points when both values fell within normal limits. NLR was defined as high if >75 th percentile in the case series. Other collected variables included tumor grade, lymphovascular invasion, margin status of resection specification and metabolic markers all in the 7 days preceding surgery. The cause of death was confirmed by review of the death certification.

Follow-Up Protocol

Patients were then subjected to after-surgery monitoring, typical after curative colon cancer resection. Serum CA125 and CEA concentrations were measured at 4-month intervals in the first year and at 6-month intervals thereafter. In addition, annual thoracoabdominalpelvic CT scans were performed to monitor for disease recurrence. Patients additionally underwent colonoscopy at 1 and 3 years after surgery. Post-CABG follow-up data were prospectively commented for 5 years or until death of the patient.

Bias and Missing Data

To reduce selection bias, we only included patients with complete follow-up and available inflammatory markers. Patients with incomplete laboratory values for m-GPS and NLR were removed from the corresponding analyses.

Statistical Analysis

Kaplan–Meier curves were used to estimate overall survival (OS) and cancer-specific survival (CSS), and group comparisons were made using the log-rank test. A multivariate analysis using the Cox proportional hazards model was conducted to control for potential confounders. Results are significant for $p < 0.05$. Data analysis was conducted using SPSS software (version 23; IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA).

Ethical Considerations

This research was conducted according to the principles laid out in the Declaration of Helsinki. No personal information about any patients was disclosed and data were kept in a secure manner (in accordance with the institutional or regulatory guidelines).

Results

Study Population and Baseline Characteristics

The study population consisted of 210 individuals who had colorectal cancer surgery and fulfilled the predefined eligibility criteria. Staging data were available for all patients, while preoperative m-GPS and

NLR values were available for 179 and 209 patients, respectively (Table 1). The cohort had a median age of 72 years, ranging from 35 to 99, with males comprising 59% of the study population. Right hemicolectomy and anterior resection were the most frequently performed

procedures, collectively representing 65% of all surgeries. Laparoscopic techniques were utilised in 58% of cases. Over 779 patient-years of follow-up, a total of 64 patients died from colon cancer, with a mean follow-up duration of 3.7 years.

Table 1: Traditional Predictors of Cancer Survival (Univariate Analysis)

Characteristic	N	CSS			
		Deaths due to cancer	5-yr survival (%)	95% CI	P value
Sex					
Male	124	36	69.5	59.9-77.2	0.313
Female	86	28	62.5	50.0-72.6	
Age (years)					
<60	35	12	65.1	46.9-78.5	0.053
60<70	49	8	84.9	70.8-92.5	
70<80	66	24	57.6	43.4-69.5	
80+	60	20	59.9	43.6-72.9	
Operative approach†					
Open	86	34	55.8	43.3-66.5	0.005
Laparoscopic	121	28	75.0	65.6-88.2	
Tumour grade†					
I	20	1	94.7	68.1-99.2	0.003
II	150	48	64.1	54.8-71.9	
III	27	12	49.9	28.8-67.9	
Lymphovascular invasion†					
Absent	103	25	72.9	62.4-80.8	0.009
Present	102	37	60.7	49.4-70.1	
Resection margin					
Negative	200	57	68.8	61.3-75.2	<0.001
Positive	10	7	22.2	3.4-51.3	
TNM Stage†					
1	36	2	93.6	76.6-98.4	<0.001
2	83	23	67.9	55.2-77.7	
3	74	25	64.1	51.3-74.5	
4	14	14	0.0	-	
Carbohydrate antigen 19-9†					
Normal	124	28	76.4	67.2-83.4	0.006
High (>27 U/ml)	32	14	52.1	32.5-68.4	
Carcinoembryonic antigen†					
Normal	119	27	74.8	65.4-82.1	0.074
High (>5 µg/L)	46	17	63.4	46.6-76.3	

Note: †Missing values: Operative approach (3), Tumour grade (13), Lymphovascular invasion (5), TNM (3), Dukes (3) Carbohydrate antigen 19-9 (54), Carcinoembryonic antigen (45). P values were determined using a log-rank test throughout.

Univariate Analysis of Prognostic Factors

Univariate analysis identified several factors associated with reduced cancer-specific 5-year survival (Table 1). These included operative approach, tumor differentiation, lymphovascular invasion, resection

margin status, TNM stage, and elevated CA19-9 levels. Among inflammatory parameters, elevated neutrophil count, high NLR, and high m-GPS were also significantly associated with adverse cancer-specific outcomes (Table 2).

Table 2. Pre-Operative Laboratory Measures and Cancer Survival (Univariate Analysis)

Characteristic	N	CSS			P value
		Deaths due to cancer	5-yr survival	95% CI	
Blood group					
A	83	19	73.9	62.0-82.6	0.141
B	20	6	63.8	36.1-82.1	
AB	8	4	50.0	15.2-77.5	
O	99	35	62.1	50.8-71.5	
Platelet count					
Normal	188	55	68.5	60.8-75.0	0.134
High (>400x10 ⁹ /L)	22	9	47.7	22.2-69.4	
Neutrophil count					
Normal	172	47	71.1	63.2-77.6	0.001
High (>7x10 ⁹ /L)	38	17	40.6	20.8-59.7	
Lymphocyte count					
Normal	166	49	68.4	60.1-75.3	0.598
Low (≤1x10 ⁹ /L)	44	15	61.2	43.9-74.6	
NLR					
Normal	157	43	71.3	62.9-78.0	0.042
≥75 th centile	53	21	52.5	36.4-66.3	
Platelet: lymphocyte ratio					
Normal	158	46	67.8	59.2-74.9	0.554
≥75 th centile	52	18	63.9	48.2-75.9	
Glasgow Score†					
0	117	24	78.3	69.1-85.0	<0.001
1	49	21	49.0	31.3-64.5	
2	14	10	25.0	6.3-49.9	

Note: P values were determined using a log-rank test throughout. † Missing values: Glasgow score (30).

Multivariate Analysis of Prognostic Factors

Multivariate analysis identified resection margin status, TNM stage, and elevated m-GPS as independent predictors of cancer mortality (Table 3). Patients with

an m-GPS of 2 exhibited a markedly increased risk of cancer-related death, with a hazard ratio of 3.92 (95% CI: 1.80–8.56; p = 0.001), compared to those with an m-GPS of 0.

Table 3. Multivariable analysis was performed on factors identified as significant predictors of cancer-specific outcomes in the univariable analysis.

		Crude relative risk of cancer-specific mortality†			Adjusted relative risk of cancer-specific mortality‡		
		Hazard ratio	95% CI	p*	Adjusted hazard ratio	95% CI	p*
Pathology							
<i>Resection margin</i>	Negative	7.60	3.40-17.01	<0.001	3.19	1.22-8.32	0.018
	Positive	---					
<i>Tumour Grade</i>	I	---					
	II	7.94	1.10-57.54	0.041	4.78	0.65-35.01	0.124
	III	15.19	1.97-116.91	0.150	7.35	0.93-57.98	0.059
<i>TNM Stage</i>	1	---					
	2	6.11	1.44-5.93	0.014	4.37	0.98-19.55	0.054

	3	7.87	1.86-3.25	0.005	6.14	1.40-27.01	0.016
	4	74.59	16.66-33.97	<0.001	52.03	9.81-275.9	<0.001
<i>Lymphovascular invasion</i>	Yes	1.95	1.17-3.25	0.010			
	No	---					
Laboratory measures							
Glasgow score	0	---					
	1	2.86	1.59-5.16	<0.001	1.86	0.98-3.52	0.057
	2	6.93	3.29-14.59	<0.001	3.92	1.80-8.56	0.001
Neutrophil-lymphocyte ratio	High ($\geq 75^{\text{th}}$ centile)	1.71	1.01-2.88	0.044			
	Normal	---					
Ca19-9	High (>27 U/ml)	2.40	1.26-4.56	0.008			
	Normal	---					

Note: †Univariable Cox regression analysis; ‡Multivariable Cox regression analysis adjusted for the listed covariates. Wald p-value.

Survival Analysis

Kaplan–Meier analysis showed that CSS significantly decreased with TNM stage and a higher m-GPS ($P < 0.01$ and $P = 0.047$, respectively; Figure 1). The subgroup

analysis also revealed that high m-GPS (scores 1–2) was associated with worse survival in patients with stage II ($P = 0.051$) and III ($P = 0.047$) disease (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Kaplan-Meier CSS Curves Stratified by TNM Stage and m-GPS

Panel (A) presents the CSS according to TNM stages I–IV, showing a stepwise decrease in the survival with increasing stage. A significant difference among TNM categories was noted with respect to survival ($p < 0.01$), which established the TNM stage as a major determinant of prognosis.

Panel (B) shows the survival curves stratified by preoperative m-GPS (scores 0, 1, and 2), indicating a significant association between high m-GPS and poor OS ($p = 0.047$, log-rank test). Patients with m-GPS = 2 had the worst survival.

Figure 2. Kaplan-Meier CSS Curves for Patients with TNM Stage II and TNM Stage III, Stratified by m-GPS

Panel (A) illustrates CSS among patients with TNM stage II disease, comparing those with m-GPS = 0 (green) and m-GPS 1–2 (orange). The survival curves suggest that an elevated m-GPS is associated with worse CSS, with a trend toward statistical significance ($p = 0.051$, log-rank test).

Panel (B) depicts survival outcomes for TNM stage III patients, stratified by m-GPS categories. A significantly lower probability of survival was observed in patients with m-GPS 1–2 compared to m-GPS 0 ($p = 0.047$, log-rank test). The separation of curves indicates a potential prognostic role for systemic inflammation in higher-stage colon cancer.

Discussion

In this study, we examined a consolidated dataset of colorectal cancer patients from a single centre to evaluate the prognostic value of preoperative NLR and m-GPS. The findings are consistent with earlier reports, particularly highlighting the prognostic relevance of m-GPS in patients undergoing surgical resection for colon cancer [8-10]. Although lymphovascular invasion has been associated with poor outcomes in large case series [11], in our cohort, it was significantly associated with CSS in univariate analysis ($p = 0.009$) but did not remain an independent predictor in the multivariate model ($p = 0.010$). This suggests that its prognostic effect may be mediated by other clinicopathological factors, such as TNM stage and resection margin status. This opinion is supported by several studies identifying a correlation between neutrophil-driven inflammation determined either by analysis of tissues or blood and colon cancer outcome [12-14]. This study did not identify a significant correlation between NLR and CSS; however, recent systematic reviews suggest that such a relationship may exist [7]. Laboratory research also supports the idea that inflammation drives cancer progression through various mechanisms including the promotion of angiogenesis, tumour invasion and inhibition of local anti-tumour immunity [15]. These processes create a pro-tumor microenvironment,

supporting immune evasion and resistance to therapy. Although no significant association was observed in this study, the established biological plausibility of NLR as a prognostic marker warrants further validation in larger appropriately powered prospective studies. The findings have shown a strong relationship between preoperative m-GPS and CSS, suggesting that the systemic inflammatory status at surgery is related to postoperative cancer relapse. This study does not explain the mechanisms connecting inflammation to cancer, however they support the concept that inflammation drives cancer development. The present association suggests that elevated m-GPS could serve as a surrogate marker of an inflammation related cancer phenotype. Further validation of these observations will be required; the next study to do this could include parallel measurement of m-GPS and tumor immune cell profiling in larger cohorts. Despite such mechanistic links being indicated and increasing clinical evidence pointing to an association between inflammation and cancer outcome, inflammatory parameters are not yet included in colon cancer staging systems. By providing further evidence for the prognostic benefit of the pre-operative m-GPS in colon cancer, this study supports a growing argument for its inclusion in clinical decision-making algorithms. That the m-GPS is inexpensive and easy to interpret provides further weight to this argument, particularly given the significant degree of inter-observer variability demonstrated in the analysis of histological parameters such as lymphovascular invasion [16]. Interestingly, the use of m-GPS to determine post-operative follow-up on patients with colon cancer is yet to be explored. Each patient in this study underwent an intensive follow-up program independent of tumour stage at presentation. The benefit of such intensive follow-up programs is unclear [16] and any improvement is likely to be small, with the number of curative recurrences detected not much higher than when follow-up consists of investigation only when symptoms appear [17].

Currently, the benefit of a follow-up program tailored to recurrence risk has not been fully explored [18], however, it is likely that such a program would dramatically reduce the cost and anxiety of follow-up, by reducing unnecessary investigation [19]. The tailoring of follow-up will rely on the assessment of multiple patient-specific factors including genetic and histological profiles. Our study indicates that analysis of the patient's inflammatory state during the pre-operative period could also help to tailor the follow-up protocol. Determination of m-GPS may also be useful for the prediction of benefits from chemotherapy. Adjuvant chemotherapy is part of the treatment algorithm for patients with stage III colon cancer 5, as it improves survival in this patient group [20,21]. However, chemotherapy in Stage II disease is more controversial, as although a significant number of these patients develop recurrence following surgery, adjuvant chemotherapy results in only a modest survival benefit when given to all stage II colon cancer patients [22]. It is therefore crucial that robust prognostic indicators are developed, enabling the clinician to identify patients within each stage who are suitable for chemotherapy whilst ensuring that patients are not unnecessarily treated. Our data suggests that elevated m-GPS could be used to identify stage II patients with a poor prognosis who may benefit from chemotherapy. M-GPS may also have a role to play in identifying patients with stage III disease in whom chemotherapy could be avoided. However, the latter statement is difficult to qualify, as the majority of such patients would have undergone adjuvant chemotherapy. Based on current research evidence we are at a state of equipoise with regards to the use of adjuvant chemotherapy for stage III colon cancer and as such it is difficult to justify a trial in which patients are denied chemotherapy based on their pre-operative m-GPS.

Limitations

This study does, however, have several limitations; for instance, single-institution analysis, findings may not be generalizable to broader populations due to potential selection bias and variations in clinical practice. While m-GPS and NLR were evaluated as inflammatory markers, other relevant biomarkers were not assessed. Missing data, particularly in laboratory parameters, may have influenced statistical power. The impact of adjuvant chemotherapy and patient compliance was not accounted for, which could affect survival outcomes. Furthermore, although the follow-up period was adequate for CSS analysis, with longer recurrence patterns were incompletely described. More prospective, multicenter trials with long-term follow-up are required to verify these results.

Conclusion

The results of the present study suggest that in patients with colon cancer receiving curative therapy m-GPS should be regarded as an independent prognostic factor of CSS. High m-GPS scores were related to poor survival, especially in stage II and III patients, indicating its potential use for risk assessment and treatment decision-making. While the TNM stage is essential for prognostication, combining inflammatory markers like m-GPS may help optimize patient selection for adjuvant therapy and individualized follow-up strategies. Further prospective validation is needed to integrate these results into the clinical approach.

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